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MODELING THE METHODOLOGY FOR PREPARING PARA-JUDO ATHLETES FOR COMPETITIVE PERFORMANCE

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Abstract. This article examines the analysis of methods that have been most frequently used and proven effective in achieving results in the competitive processes of para-judo athletes. Additionally, it explores effective ways to organize training sessions and further develop training methodologies through specialized exercises. The study also includes an analysis and development of exercises aimed at enhancing the training process for para-judo athletes.

Keywords: task, process, training, method, development, educational training, exercises, classification, direction, sports schools, efficiency.

INTRODUCTION

Ongoing research by scholars worldwide focuses on enhancing the reaction speed of para-judo athletes, improving their physical preparedness for major competitions, and refining the methodology for teaching technical techniques.

One of the primary objectives of parasport training is to develop the skills and competencies of para-judo athletes in applying effective methods used during training. The volume and intensity of the methods employed, as well as the progression of training loads, are systematically planned throughout the training process. These training sessions are designed to replicate the tactical preparation structure of competitive matches. Consequently, the increasing frequency and systematic execution of techniques during training contribute to their continuous refinement and improvement.

The process of enhancing the skills, preparedness, and movement techniques of para-judo athletes is carried out over a specific period, divided into stages such as initial learning, reinforcement, and further improvement. During the initial learning phase, athletes develop the necessary conceptual understanding to execute technical movements correctly. However, if these skills are not further developed, and if movements lack sufficient precision in terms of timing and spatial accuracy, issues such as muscle tension inconsistencies, unnecessary movements, and increased fatigue may arise, ultimately leading to a decline in performance.

In this regard, para-judo athletes often expend excessive energy, executing competitive movements with significant strain on various muscle groups, which disrupts the integrity of technical phases. Quick fatigue indicates an insufficient level of work capacity in para-judo athletes.

Para-judo athletes frequently encounter these challenges during competitions but overcome them with strong determination and resilience. This serves as a valuable learning experience for beginner para-judo athletes in training programs, playing a crucial role in their development and preparation.

According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5924, dated January 24, 2020, "On Measures for the Further Development and Popularization of Physical Culture and Sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan," as well as Resolution No. PQ-5281, dated November 5, 2021, "On the Comprehensive Preparation of Uzbek Athletes for the XXXIII Summer Olympic Games and the XVII Paralympic Games to be Held in Paris (France) in 2024," and Resolution No. PQ-286, dated June 20, 2022, "On Measures for the Further Development of Judo," this study contributes to the

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implementation of tasks outlined in various regulatory and legal documents. It also plays a role in increasing the popularity of judo as an Olympic sport, improving the system for selecting talented young athletes, and advancing the overall development of the field.

Research Objective:

to enhance the organization and effectiveness of training sessions by developing a competition model for para-judo athletes.

Research Tasks:

- to identify errors and deficiencies in the process of introducing techniques to visually impaired para-judo athletes and teaching them these techniques;
- preparing athletes for competitions through the development of a comprehensive training program and model for para-judo athletes.

To investigate the impact of training load planning efficiency on the dynamics of sports performance parameters in para-athletes, we conducted research during the second phase of our initial experiment. In this study, we assessed the general and specific physical preparedness of para-judokas, analyzing the dynamics of various training load parameters to evaluate changes in their physical readiness levels.

Furthermore, throughout the course of the experiment, the degree of statistical correlation between the different aspects of para-judo athletes' overall preparation and the various parameters of their training loads was carefully evaluated. Additionally, the study examined how training loads, applied in different directions, influenced the para-athletes' physical condition, while also considering the impact on the multiple dimensions of their preparation.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Para-athletes were selected for these groups based on having similar levels of sports skill and values for various aspects of their preparation indicators.

Group 1 – Applied the training loads in the direction proposed by our methodology.

Group 2 – Applied the anaerobic-aerobic training loads typical of the traditional preparation system for para-judo athletes.

The weekly microcycle of pre-competition preparation for para-judokas in the initial training stage.

Days of the week	Means (Training Tools)	Performance Standards	Physiological Regimen
Monday	Preparatory Exercises <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One of the most common throwing techniques; • Throwing the opponent over the shoulder; • Pushing the opponent's inner part with the hand to execute a throw. 	Athlete 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Osae-komi – controlling and holding the opponent down on the ground. Athlete 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shime-waza – applying pressure on the neck or executing a choke to force the opponent into submission. Recovery: 2-minute rest for recovery.	Aerobic

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	<p>Technical Exercises</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Achieving coordination between foot and hand movements during gripping positions; • Working with opponents with contrasting styles; • Performing pull-ups on a bar; • Practicing with a mannequin. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hold the opponent and place one hand on their shoulder. • Bring the opponent onto your shoulder and quickly throw them backward. • Use your other hand to grip the opponent's arm. <p>Recovery: 2-minute rest for recovery.</p>	
Wednesday	<p>Preparatory Exercises</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Performing feint movements while executing the Nage Waza technique; • Creating opportunities to transition into the Katame-waza technique using feints. 	<p>Athlete 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Executing the Nage Waza technique to throw the opponent from various positions. <p>Athlete 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transitioning into the Katame-waza technique and, when noticed by the opponent, switching to a secondary feint technique for 10 minutes. <p>Recovery: 2-3 minutes rest for recovery.</p>	Aerobic
	<p>Technical Exercises</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practicing feint movements using the legs; • Practicing feint movements using the body. 	<p>Athlete 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entering and exiting the Nage Waza technique or a continuous secondary technique using feint movements for 10 minutes. <p>Athlete 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entering and exiting the Katame-waza technique or a continuous secondary technique using feint movements for 10 minutes. <p>Recovery: 2-3 minutes rest for recovery.</p>	
Friday	<p>Preparatory Exercises</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Executing techniques in motion; • Maintaining proper technical execution while performing techniques in motion. 	<p>Athlete 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Performing various techniques in motion, repeating each 10 times; <p>Athlete 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Performing various techniques in motion, repeating each 10 times. 	Aerobic
	<p>Technical Exercises</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Repeating technical elements of techniques using a mannequin and resistance bands. 	<p>Athlete 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Performing techniques in motion with light resistance from the opponent for 10 minutes. <p>Athlete 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Performing techniques in motion with light resistance from the opponent for 10 minutes. <p>Recovery: 2-3 minutes rest for recovery.</p>	

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<p>Special Exercises</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rotating a 2 kg dumbbell around the head while attached to the belt (25 times); • Holding a 2 kg dumbbell with both hands and rotating it around the head (25 times). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rotating a 2 kg dumbbell around the head while attached to the belt for 3 minutes; • Holding a 2 kg dumbbell with both hands and rotating it around the head for 3 minutes. 	
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Note: The performance standards of exercises in the weekly microcycles are adjusted based on the physiological and functional condition of the athletes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Using training loads with a single directional focus to develop a specific ability during an individual session or a series of training sessions has been shown to have a deeper but more limited impact on the human body compared to comprehensive loads. In practice, various combinations of selective training loads are frequently employed. For example, in a single training session, a cross-country skier may develop aerobic endurance solely by moving with motorized skis. However, this exercise must be performed using different methodological approaches: initially with an interval method, followed by a steady-state method, or vice versa. Similarly, within a single training session, a set of different tools with the same directional focus may be utilized.

In this context, para-judokas often exert excessive physical effort due to the nature of competitive movements, which require significant muscle engagement across the body. This can lead to disruptions in the integrity of technical phases when executing techniques. Rapid fatigue among para-judokas is indicative of an insufficient level of work capacity.

During competitions, para-judokas frequently encounter such challenges. However, thanks to their strong willpower, they courageously overcome these difficulties. This resilience plays a crucial role in shaping the training and development of beginner-level para-judokas, making their training process a significant learning experience.

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A Set of Exercises Aimed at Improving the Physical Qualities and Technical-Tactical Preparation of Para-Judokas

In the first stage of our research, we analyzed the technical methods used by leading para-judokas during training sessions. According to our findings, when preparing for prestigious competitions, para-judokas, with the assistance of their coaches, first study and analyze information about their weight category and all participants within that category. This process constitutes their tactical preparation for victory. Such an approach indicates that in high-level competitions, preparation involves the execution of complex tactical movements based on deeply assimilated technical methods.

The development of a long-term training program is of great importance for the effective management of the preparation process for para-judokas. A well-structured program that considers the multi-year training phases enables a more precise determination of the priority directions in the educational and training process of para-judokas. Additionally, it facilitates the establishment of specific performance indicators and serves as a foundation for assessing and improving their preparedness for judo. Throughout our research, these aspects are considered and refined to enhance the training process.

The primary distinction of our research methodology lies in integrating more effective technical and tactical movements—commonly utilized by non-disabled judokas—into the training structure of para-judokas. This approach aims to develop a dynamic stereotype that closely resembles actual competition conditions.

Thus, our findings suggest that applying this research-based training methodology in the preparation process of para-judokas enables us to implement practical strategies to enhance their readiness for the extreme conditions of competitive performance.

Optimizing the training process for para-athletes should be effectively implemented during their youth. This period is marked by significant skeletal growth, with an annual height increase of

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approximately 6–9 cm and a body mass index gain of 4.5–9 kg. The increase in height primarily results from the growth of the upper body. As muscle fibers develop, they struggle to keep pace with the longitudinal growth of tubular bones, leading to changes in body proportions. However, in para-athletes, physical development tends to be slower.

Well-developed motor skills enable para-athletes to select a more effective set of technical and tactical movements that align with their individual abilities. This, in turn, creates a foundation for the optimal improvement of para-sports performance.

Based on literature sources, surveys of para-judo specialists, and video analysis of competitive matches, our research aimed to identify the most effective technical and tactical actions used by highly skilled para-judokas. The results of these studies have enabled us to justify and develop an experimental methodology for preparing para-judokas for competitive performance.

The theoretical foundation for substantiating the research methodology is based on the following principles and rules of sports training: the principle of unity and interrelation between the structure of competitive activity and training, as well as the principles of feasibility and individualization.

The principle of unity and interrelation between the structure of competitive activity and training was considered in our study from the perspective that the targeted construction of the training process should shape an optimal competitive activity system, ensuring success in competition.

This is only possible if there is a clear interrelation between the factors and conditions determining the effectiveness of competitive performance, as well as between the structure of competition and the structure of an athlete's preparation. Such interrelation necessitates precisely defining the relationships between the primary and supplementary components of the integrated structure of competitive activity.

The degree of interrelation between competition and training activities can be determined by considering the characteristics of the sport and its developmental traditions, ensuring that training methodologies are aligned with the demands of high-level competition.

The principle of execution and individualization guided our interest in determining the defining rules for specifying requirements based on an athlete's individual level of training, their stage of preparation, and the conditions and mode of sports activity.

The primary distinction of our research methodology lies in incorporating highly effective technical and tactical actions—those employed by elite wrestlers—into the training programs of young wrestlers. This is done to develop a dynamic stereotype that closely mimics actual competition scenarios, ensuring optimal preparation for competitive matches.

Our research considers integrating the most effective technical and tactical actions—those applied by skilled para-judo athletes in real competitive settings – into the training program for para-judo practitioners. This approach includes:

- Technical preparation, which involves not only mastering the general techniques but also deliberately studying and refining the more effective technical-tactical maneuvers employed by elite para-judo athletes.
- Technical-tactical preparation, which consists of learning and improving combinations of traditional judo techniques with at least one Katame Waza technical maneuver.
- Tactical preparation, which focuses on developing strategic scenarios that facilitate the application of Katame Waza techniques.

The experimental methodology considers distributing the volume of training means across different preparation types based on the training phase. For example, during a single training session:

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- in the preparatory phase, 40% of the time was allocated to technical training, whereas during the competition phase, this was reduced to 20%.
- for technical-tactical and tactical training, 20% of the time was assigned in the preparatory phase, while this increased to 40% in the competition phase.

Beyond these differences observed during the experiment, and in accordance with recommendations from parasport specialists, the training sessions for the experimental group extensively utilized various means and methods for the technical-tactical improvement of para-judo athletes. In our view, these approaches should be designed to closely simulate competitive conditions, ensuring optimal adaptation to real match environments:

- creating favorable conditions by the training partner to facilitate the execution of technical-tactical movements in standard judo situations;
- increasing resistance from the partner during training bouts to make executing one technique more challenging while making another easier, thereby refining skill adaptation;
- evaluating only highly effective (Katame Waza) throws during training matches;
- doubling the score for successfully executed Katame Waza throws in training bouts.

Thus, in our view, applying the experimental methodology in para-judo training enables us to implement realistic training approaches that enhance para-athletes' readiness for extreme competitive conditions.

CONCLUSION

Modeling training sessions for para-judo athletes primarily incorporates leading methods that have proven to be effective. These methods are integrated into the training process to ensure ease of learning and maximum efficiency for athletes engaged in parasports.

The training methodology considers the distribution of training tools according to different preparation stages. For example, During the preparatory phase, 40% of the time was allocated to technical training, while 20% was dedicated to it during the competition phase. For technical-tactical and tactical training, 20% of the time was allotted during the preparatory phase, increasing to 40% in the competition phase.

Beyond these differences, and in accordance with recommendations from parasport specialists, the experimental group's training sessions actively utilized various technical-tactical development tools and methods. Based on our analysis, we recommend aligning these training approaches as closely as possible to real competitive conditions for optimal results.

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